

Phytochemical Investigation of *Vateria indica*

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VATERIA indica (Fam. : Dipterocarpaceae) occurs in the evergreen forests of the Western Ghats from North Kanara to Kerala in India. The resin (white Dammar) of the tree and Dhupa fat of the seeds are commercially important and have medicinal¹ uses also. The bark² and seeds³ have already been examined for their chemical constituents.

The present communication reports the chemical constituents of the leaves and roots collected from Karnataka state (India). The column chromatography of the combined acetone and alcohol extract of the leaves over silica gel gave two pure compounds A and B. The same compounds were isolated from the roots. Compound A (1%) was crystallised from aqueous ethanol as rectangular prisms, m.p. 154–56°. It was identified as bergenin⁴ a C-glucoside by uv, nmr and superimposable ir spectra. Compound B (0.42%) was crystallised from chloroform–methanol as white solid, m.p. > 350°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –400° (MeOH). The uv, ir, nmr, mass spectra and C and H analyses were comparable with those reported for hopeaphenol⁴; B being identified as hopeaphenol.

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The ¹³C nmr spectra of hopeaphenol (not reported earlier) in DMSO-d₆ showed the following resonances. Three aliphatic doublets for six non-oxygenated carbons (one signal swamped by DMSO, 47.17, 48.40 ppm), one aliphatic doublet at 86.83

ppm for two aliphatic oxygenated carbons, eight aromatic doublets for 24 aromatic carbons (94.13 to 129.04), six quaternary carbon singlets (116.81 to 140.59) for twelve carbon atoms and six phenolic singlets (154.58 to 157.86) for 12 carbons (the designation singlet and doublet refer to the appearance of the resonance in the single frequency off resonance mode experiments). Probable assignment based on substituent parameters⁵ are shown in structure of hopeaphenol (1).

This is the first report of the occurrence of bergenin and hopeaphenol in the leaves and roots. The leaves can be used as a source of bergenin as it occurs in 1% yield. Hopeaphenol was found fungicidal against two wood rotting fungi, namely, *Poria monticola* (at 0.05 and 0.1% level) and *Polyporus versicolor* (at 0.1% level).

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Surface Hydrocarbons from the Leaves of some *Cassia* Species

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It is a well known fact that surface lipids have a vital role in conducting transpiration and leaf surface properties. Moreover, the composition of lipids and particularly hydrocarbon distribution, has also been suggested as a parameter in chemotaxonomy¹⁻⁴. But this approach has not always met with unambiguous success⁵⁻⁷ since wax composition may vary not only with the environmental history but also with the age of the